

Isolation, Characterization and a Study of the Solvolytic Reactions in Non-aqueous Media of some Dioxomolybdenum (VI) Chelates and the Solvolytic Studies in Methanol of a few other Dioxomolybdenum (VI) Complexes with Monoligands

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Two dioxomolybdenum (VI) chelates having the compositions $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$ [$\text{Sal}_2\text{en} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{N}, \text{N}'\text{-disalicyl ethylenediimine}$] are isolated by reacting $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the appropriate ligands in suitable solvents and they have been characterised by i.r., TGA and magnetic susceptibility studies. The former undergoes 'base solvolysis' and the latter 'acid solvolysis' in methanol as followed by their conductance measurement in the said solvent. Such conductance study reveals that the complexes $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{pyridine}, 4\text{-nitropyridine}$ and quinoline N-oxides; triphenyl phosphine oxide; hexamethyl phosphoramidate and dimethyl sulphoxide) also undergo 'base solvolysis' in methanol but at a very high dilution ($\sim 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) the triphenyl phosphine oxide, quinoline N-oxide and dimethyl sulphoxide complexes probably undergo further decomposition (a maxima in $\sqrt{C_M}$ vs. Λ_M plots) when the organic ligand molecules leave the inner sphere of coordination and the solvated organic ligands associate with the protons to a marked extent. This observation suggests that the standard free energy change accompanying the transfer of H^+ [$\Delta G_t^\circ (\text{H}^+)$] from methanol to the methanolated ligand species in these three cases are negative. A probable qualitative theoretical model in the case of the DMSO complexes has also been incorporated.

ISOLATION and characterization of dioxomolybdenum (VI) complexes with a number of unidentate neutral ligands have been reported by us recently¹⁻³. So far as the dioxomolybdenum (VI) chelates are concerned, air stable products having the compositions MoO_2L ($\text{LH}_2 = \text{various diprotic quadridentate Schiff bases}$)⁴ and MoO_2L_2 ($\text{LH} = 8\text{-hydroxy quinoline}$)⁵ are quite well known. With ethylene diamine and triethylene tetramine, solids of variable composition probably containing polymolybdates have also been obtained⁶. Herein is reported the isolation and characterization by some physicochemical studies of two dioxomolybdenum (VI) chelates, viz., $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$, obtained by reacting the respective organic ligands with $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (not perfectly free from HCl vapours absorbed during preparation) in suitable organic solvent. However, when the Schiff base, N,N'-disalicyl ethylene diimine reacts with $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in alcohol containing excess of sodium acetate the compound $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$ is formed. We have recently studied⁷⁻⁹ the solvolytic equilibria of different complexes of metal oxocations in non-aqueous media

and the present study is also extended to the solvolysis study, in non-aqueous medium, of these two chelates as also some other complexes of the type $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{pyridine}, 4\text{-nitropyridine}$ and quinoline N-oxides; triphenyl phosphine oxide; hexamethyl phosphoramidate and dimethyl sulphoxide) isolated by us^{1,2}.

Characterization and physico-chemical studies :

The infrared data (Table 1) of the complex $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{en})$ show that this complex is not like one where ethylene diamine functions as a trans ligand¹⁰ leading to polymeric chains. Probably ethylenediamine, here, serves as a chelate former in planar cis or in gauche conformation¹¹. Insolubility of the complex in chloroform or in any other suitable solvent foils the possibility of n.m.r. measurement to resolve whether the chelate is a planar cis- or is in gauche conformation. Though i.r. data have been used in such cases by some previous workers¹¹, that would not be much convincing in the present case since the characteristic bands around 900 cm^{-1} are obscured by very strong $\text{Mo} = \text{O}$ stretching bands due to cis MoO_2 group, one at 876 and the other at 930 cm^{-1} region.

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TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS AND THEIR QUALITATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF THE COMPLEX $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$.

Band heads (cm^{-1})	Assignment
910(s), 890(sh)	CH_2 rock ¹¹
706(s,b) 780(m) 836(m)	Further components of CH_2 rocks in chelated structures ^{11,12} .
876(s) 930(s)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{Mo}=\text{O})^{13,14}$
1008(m) 1034(s) 1084(m)	C-N or C-C stretch (coupled) ¹²
1320(w), 1338(w)	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ wag. ¹¹
<i>D</i>	
1500(s)	$\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ wag. ¹¹
1570(sh) 1600(s)	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ scissors ¹¹
2800–3100(s,b)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{N-H})^{11,15}$.

The infrared spectral data (Table 2) of Sal_2enH_2 and of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{enH}_2)\text{Cl}_2$ show that in the pure ligand a medium intensity broad band is centered at 3350 cm^{-1} due to the presence of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded^{15,16} O-H group and even in the complex this band is found at 3400 cm^{-1} and is rather sharp. This may be due to uncoordinated O-H groups and the sharpness may be due to lack of hydrogen bonding after complex formation. MoO_2 group, here also, has the cis configuration (C_{2v}) since both ν_1 and ν_3 of the said group are i.r. active (Table 2).

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS AND THEIR QUALITATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF Sal_2enH_2 AND $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{enH}_2)\text{Cl}_2$.

Compound and band heads (cm^{-1})	Compound and band heads (cm^{-1})	Assignment
Sal_2enH_2	$\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{enH}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	
740(s) 748(s) 758(sh) 775(m) 850(s) 860(s) 865(sh) 896(m) 936(m)	700(s) 756(s) 796(m) 818(w) 884(m)	$\pi(\text{C-H})^{15}$
—	808(s) 936(s) 944(m)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{Mo}=\text{O})^{14,17}$
<i>D</i>		
1040(s)	1036(m)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{C-H aliph})^{15}$
1020(s) 1146(s) 1196(m) 1220(m) 1248(w)	1014(m) 1084(w) 1154(m) 1218(sh) 1230(s)	$\rho(\text{C-H})^{15}$
1410(s) 1454(s)	1434(m) 1474(s)	$\bar{\nu}(>\text{C}=\text{C}<)$ and $\bar{\nu}(\text{C}=\text{N}-)^{15}$
1488(s) 1498(sh) 1574(s) 1600(m) 1628(s)	1500(m) 1536(w) 1600(s) 1645(s)	
1310(w) 1370(m)	1328(w) 1396(w)	O-H in plane def. ¹⁵
1276(s) 1290(sh]	1276(m) 1280(sh)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{C-O})$ aromatic ^{15,16} .
1110(m)	1120(m)	C-OH bending ¹⁵
2860(w) 2900(w)	2860(w) 2900(w,b)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{C-H aliph.})$ sym and asym. ¹⁵
—	3000(s)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{C-H aromatic})^{15}$
3350(m)	3400(s)	$\bar{\nu}(\text{O-H})^{15}$.

The molar magnetic susceptibility value of MoO_2^{2+} ion in the ethylenediamine and in the Schiff base chelate are 89×10^{-6} and 111×10^{-6} e.m.u. mole⁻¹ respectively, indicating slight paramagnetism in systems where $S = 0$. TIP might be a possible attribute^{13,18} but in some cases we observed^{1,2} negative values also for the corrected molar susceptibility of MoO_2^{2+} ion.

The TGA curves show that the ethylenediamine adduct is thermally very stable and decomposes only above 245° which precludes the possibility of there being any coordinated water or any other associated solvent molecules. The Schiff base chelate starts to decompose at 112° and the decomposition is complete at 514° giving MoO_3 as the final ignited product. Both the compounds, however, do not furnish any intermediate stable products.

These two compounds are moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile. The Schiff base chelate is also slightly soluble in dichloromethane in which solvent the compound is practically a non-electrolyte. In acetonitrile solvent even a very dilute solution ($\sim 10^{-4}M$) of both the complexes shows a molar conductance value in the range of $8\text{--}10\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$. This suggests that the chloro groups in both these chelates are within the coordination sphere. But, as usual the complexes undergo extensive solvolytic reactions in methanol which is very common to the substitution labile complexes studied by the present authors⁷⁻⁹ and the conductance—concentration data (Table 3) suggests that in the case of Schiff base chelate, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{enH}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$, probably 'acid solvolysis' occurs in accordance with the equilibria expressed by the following reaction :

Assuming 2 : 1 electrolytic behaviour¹⁹ from the above scheme, as also apparent from the Λ_M values (Table 3), the \sqrt{C} and Λ are calculated and plotted against each other. From such a plot (Fig. I-B) an approximate Λ_0 value (by free hand extrapolation; Fig. I-B) has been found to be $158\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$. A fairly accurate Λ_0 value and the equilibrium constant of the above solvolytic reaction are evaluated²⁰ in the same way as has been done for the dioxouranium (VI) complexes^{7,8}. The relevant data calculated for the Fuoss and Kraus²¹ treatment are given in Table 4 and a plot of $F(Z)/\Lambda$ vs. $C\Lambda(Y_{\pm})^2/F(Z)$ is shown in Fig. 2, wherefrom the Λ_0 and K for the Schiff base chelate are found to be $145\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ and 8.09×10^{-4} , respectively.

The ethylenediamine chelate, on the other hand, undergoes more extensive solvolysis in methanol as is clear from the conductance—concentration data (Table 3) and an extrapolation to zero concentration of Λ vs. \sqrt{C} plot (Fig. I-A) gives an approximate

Fig. 1. \sqrt{C} vs. Λ plots of (A) $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$ and (B) $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en H}_2)\text{Cl}_2$ in methanol at 25° .

Fig. 2. $F(Z)/\Lambda$ vs. $C\Lambda(Y_{\pm})^2/F(Z)$ plots of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en H}_2)\text{Cl}_2$ in methanol at 25° .

Λ_0 value which agrees well with that of HCl in methanol¹⁹. This, along with the comparison of such high Λ_M values at particular concentrations, if adjudged in the light of our recent work⁷⁻⁹ we conclude that probably 'base solvolysis' occurs in this case in methanol and as such the equilibrium as given in the following equation exists there :

So, the Λ and C values for the said plot (Fig. I-A) have been calculated from Λ_M and C_M considering that two moles of HCl are liberated per mole of the complex as per above equation.

TABLE 3—MOLAR CONDUCTANCES OF $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$ AND $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en H}_2)\text{Cl}_2$ AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS IN METHANOL AT 25°

Compound $\text{MoO}_2(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2$		Compound $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en H}_2)\text{Cl}_2$	
Concentration $(\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^2)$	Λ_M $(\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2)$	Concentration $(\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^2)$	Λ_M $(\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2)$
3.37	222	5.20	152
2.70	234	4.16	162
1.91	260	2.94	184
1.65	268	2.55	198
1.35	282	2.08	210
0.953	308	1.47	232
		1.04	254

TABLE 4—CONDUCTANCE DATA AND OTHER CALCULATED PARAMETERS FOR $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Sal}_2\text{en H}_2)\text{Cl}_2$ IN METHANOL AT 25°

C	Λ	$\sqrt{C}\Lambda$	Z	$F(Z)^*$	$\frac{F(Z)}{\Lambda}$	$\frac{C\Lambda^{**}}{F(Z)\Lambda_0}$	$\frac{\Lambda C(Y_{\pm})^{2\mp}}{F(Z)}$
0.002708	76	0.4536	0.1676	0.7756	0.0121	0.001679	0.0764
0.001733	81	0.3746	0.1632	0.8197	0.0101	0.001084	0.0630
0.000866	92	0.2823	0.1229	0.8681	0.0095	0.000575	0.0443
0.000650	99	0.2537	0.1105	0.8824	0.0089	0.000462	0.0379
0.000433	105	0.2132	0.0929	0.9022	0.0086	0.000319	0.0293
0.000217	116	0.1587	0.0691	0.9283	0.0080	0.000172	0.0182
0.000108	127	0.1171	0.0510	0.9476	0.0075	0.000092	0.0108

$$*F(Z) = 4/3 \cos^2 1/3 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{-3\sqrt{3}Z}{2} \right)$$

$$**\frac{C\Lambda}{F(Z)\Lambda_0} = \alpha C; \neq \log(Y_{\pm}) = -S_f \sqrt{\alpha C}$$

$$= -6.597 \sqrt{\alpha C} \text{ (for methanol at 25°).}$$

Similar base solvolysis in methanol solvent also occurs in the cases of the complexes of the type $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2$ ($L =$ pyridine, 4-nitro pyridine and quinoline N-oxides; triphenyl phosphine oxide; hexamethyl phosphoramidate and dimethyl sulphoxide, previously isolated and characterized by us^{1,2}. Here also the Λ_M values increase with the decreasing concentration of the complexes (Table 5) showing that the chloride ions were initially coordinated to the dioxomolybdenum (VI) ion but at infinite dilution these Λ_M values correspond to the values of 2 : 2 electrolyte in the said solvent¹⁹. Such a state of affair points to the 'base solvolysis' and the existing equilibria in the methanol solvent can be expressed as :

As usual Λ and C values are calculated from Λ_M and C_M and the plot of \sqrt{C} vs. Λ (Fig. 3) and an extrapolation to zero concentration (Λ_0) in the cases of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{PyO}$, $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HMPA}$ and $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2(4\text{-NO}_2\text{PyO})$, the Λ_0 values correspond closely to the reported Λ_0 value of HCl in methanol¹⁹.

Fig. 3. \sqrt{C} vs. Λ plots of (A) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2PyO}$, (B) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2HMPA}$ and (C) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2(4-NO}_2\text{PyO)}$ in CH_3OH at 25°.

But in the cases of the complexes $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2Ph}_3\text{PO}$, $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2QO}$ and $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2DMSO}$ the data in Table 5 show that the values of molar conductances increase gradually with the decrease of the molar concentration in methanol upto a certain extent of dilution after which the lowering of the conductance value is observed revealing a maxima in $\sqrt{C_M}$ vs. Λ_M plot (Fig. 4). This behaviour of the above mentioned compounds tends to suggest a two stage equilibria^{7,9,22} depending on dilution. At moderate dilution the equilibrium as expressed in eqn. (3) exists, but at higher dilution the compounds decompose further liberating free ligands (Ph_3PO , QO and DMSO) as indicated by eq. (4)

Fig. 4. $\sqrt{C_M}$ vs. Λ_M plots of (A) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2Ph}_3\text{PO}$, (B) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2QO}$ and (C) $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{2DMSO}$ in CH_3OH at 25°.

where L = Ph₃PO, QO or DMSO. Due to stronger ion-dipole interaction, the protons are associated with the liberated organic ligands (present in 1 : 1 mole ratio) more strongly, leading to a decrease in conductance values.

This difference of behaviour between the two sets of compounds, *viz.*, PyO, 4-NO₂PyO and HMPA complexes and Ph₃PO, QO and DMSO complexes might be accounted for by supposing that (a) in the former compounds the decomposition as mentioned by eq. (4) does not occur or (b) even if the decomposition occurs, the proton prefers to remain weakly solvated in methanol rather than to be strongly associated with these organic ligands (PyO, 4-NO₂PyO and HMPA). This argument would dictate that $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ [standard free energy change accompanying the transfer of H⁺] from methanol to methanol-DMSO, methanol-Ph₃PO and methanol-QO (obviously, in all these mixed systems, the mole fraction of DMSO, Ph₃PO and QO are quite low) should be negative and as argued in (b) if we suppose that the other complexes are also decomposed, then the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ of the analogous mixed systems should be positive.

Unfortunately, the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values between methanol and these mixed systems are not yet reported, but there is certain extent of work²³⁻²⁵ regarding the evaluation of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ between water and water-methanol mixture and also between water and water-DMSO mixture. From the results obtained by these workers^{23,24}, it becomes apparent that $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ in water to water-DMSO mixture is much more negative than that of water to water-methanol mixture. It has also been shown by Khoo²⁵ that the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{ch})$ [ch = pure chemical effect; $\Delta G_t^0(\text{el})$ (el = electrostatic) by simple Born equation] of Li⁺ ion (a hard acid like H⁺) in equimole fraction composition in DMSO-water is much more negative (-14.03) than that observed in methanol-water system (-3.67). Since the $\Delta G_t^0(\text{ch})(i)$ [i = ions, H⁺ or Li⁺] should be dominated by the electrostatic forces in between the ions and the $w_s\Delta^-$ of the respective solvent complexes, the observed difference in $\Delta G_t^0(\text{ch})(i)$ values in the two systems seems to indicate that $w_s\Delta^-$ in DMSO-water mixture exceeds that in methanol water mixture at the corresponding compositions. We may extrapolate the idea and conclude that this would apply in the case of pure methanol as well as pure DMSO and hence the standard free energy of transfer of H⁺ between methanol and methanol-DMSO mixture should be negative and so hydrogen ion would be more firmly bound by methanol-DMSO solvent complex than by the pure methanol. That is why the conductivity falls at a higher dilution when the DMSO is supposed to be liberated from the complex spheres.

An extrapolation of the above behaviour would be framed in the following way. Since H⁺ is a typical hard acid it would prefer to bind to the O-centre of DMSO. Now the H-bonded 'Structured' methanol and DMSO-methanol mixture can be represented in Fig. 5. The inductive effect of two methyl groups

will enhance the polarization of the sulphoxide group and would result in the negative charge in the oxygen atom of the DMSO molecule being greater than that on the oxygen atom in methanol molecule which contains only one methyl group. In the mixed DMSO-methanol system the effect would be transmitted to methanol molecule through the cooperative nature of the H-bonding²⁶ so that all the molecules in the mixture will be more basic than molecules in pure methanol. Higher polarizability and dipole moment of DMSO ($\alpha = 9.65 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3$ and $\mu = 4.3 \text{ D}$)²⁷ than that of methanol ($\alpha = 3.20 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3$ and $\mu = 1.70 \text{ D}$)²⁷ also partly substantiate such possibility.

From our observed data (Table 5) we can also predict that the mixed systems, *viz.*, Ph₃PO-methanol and QO-methanol would also be more basic than pure methanol alone

So, it may be concluded that conductance-concentration data in analogous complex species sometimes can be used as a reasonable guide in assessing the direction of a chemically significant thermodynamic quantity.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine are of Reagent grade (B.D.H.) material.

The Schiff base N,N'-disalicyl ethylenediimine was prepared by the usual method²⁸ and the composition was confirmed by microanalysis (C, H and N).

Preparation of the complexes :

1. Dichloro (ethylenediamine) dioxomolybdenum (VI) : MoO₂Cl₂H₂O (2 g.) in 25 ml. acetonitrile was treated with 0.6 g. of ethylenediamine with constant stirring to furnish white crystals which were filtered off, washed first with acetonitrile and then with light petroleum and air dried, yield 2.2 g. [Found : N, 10.90; Cl, 27.31 and Mo, 36.90%; MoO₂(H₂NCH₂CH₂NH₂)Cl₂ requires, N, 10.81; Cl, 27.41 and Mo, 37.07%].

2. Dichloro (N,N'-disalicyl ethylenediimine) dioxomolybdenum (VI) : N,N'-disalicyl ethylenediimine (1.85 g.) in 25 ml. of ethanol was refluxed and to this were added MoO₂Cl₂H₂O (1.5 g.) and the refluxing was again continued for 30 min. The orange-red crystals separated were filtered, washed first with a small volume of ethanol and finally with light petroleum and dried in vacuum, yield 3 g. [Found : C, 41.20; H, 3.46; N, 5.92; Cl, 15.12 and Mo, 20.42%; MoO₂(C₁₆H₁₆O₂N₂)Cl₂ requires, C, 41.11; H, 3.43; N, 6.00; Cl, 15.20 and Mo, 20.56%].

Purification of solvents :

The G.R. (E. Merck) quality methanol and dichloromethane were distilled before use. Acetonitrile was treated with P₂O₅, kept for two days and then distilled. The middle fractions of the solvents so purified were used for the conductance measurements.

Fig. 5. Charge distribution in (A) 'structured' methanol (pure) and (B) methanol-DMSO hydrogen bonded species.

TABLE 5—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF SOME DIOXOMOLYBDENUM (VI) COMPLEXES IN METHANOL AT 25°

Compound	Molar concentrations ($\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^2$)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2PyO Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	7.45 142	4.71 184	3.33 212	2.11 246	1.05 290	0.86 306	0.70 316
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2(4-NO ₂ -PyO) Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	6.43 188	4.07 224	2.88 248	2.03 278	1.02 318	0.83 332	0.68 342
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2HMPA Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	6.43 170	4.55 196	2.88 230	2.03 254	1.29 296	0.91 314	0.68 330
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2Ph ₃ PO Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	5.47 190	3.87 208	2.99 222	2.44 236	1.73 240	1.22 230	1.09 226
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2QO Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	5.75 164	3.64 206	2.57 234	1.63 258	1.15 260	0.939 258	0.545 248
MoO ₂ Cl ₂ ·2DMSO Λ_M (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	6.36 166	4.02 208	2.84 238	1.80 260	1.27 268	0.90 266	0.60 258

Instruments :

Magnetic measurements were made by the Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate (II) as a standard.

Infrared spectra were studied in KBr disc and recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer equipped with sodium chloride optics. The chart papers were calibrated by polystyrene bands at 1603 and 906 cm⁻¹.

A Chevenard's Thermobalance of type 3 of ADAMEL of Paris was used to record the thermal analysis curve upto 700°. The rate of heating was 5°/min, on the average.

Conductance of the solutions were measured in Phillips PR 9500 instrument with the help of two stoppered cells—one having a cell factor of 1.50 and the other 1.36. Both the cells gave exactly the same values of molar conductances. All measurements were made at 25° in a well-regulated thermostat with the help of a thermometer capable of recording a change of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The solvents and the solution of complex species were always kept in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride and every possible precaution was taken to prevent moisture contamination during use. Because of the uncertainties of the

instruments we preferred not to incorporate Λ_M values in nearest whole number—the values referred are either in even numbers or in multiples of five.

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